

«PHONETIC STYLES CLASSIFICATION OF POPULAR SCIENCE TEXT»

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Annotation. *Gestures have emphatic, emotive and regulative functions. The nature of interaction of kinetic and prosodic means is determined by the aim of the utterance. One of the interesting points of this interaction is the opportunity to discern lies if prosodic and kinetic signs do not match: even a trained person is unable to control micromotion of facial muscles and some minor gestures, what is immediately noticed by our subconscious.*

Key words: *Discovery channel, interaction, utterance, interaction, prosodic, unable, facial muscles, kinetic signs, trained person, minor gestures.*

The variations of phonetic styles are based on the typical speech situations. As far as prepared speech is concerned, there are several factors that distinguish these speech situations:

The audience

The setting

The purpose of speech

Here the setting can determine the degree of formality of the communication; the target audience determines the content, style and the 'tone' of speech. According to the purpose set by the speaker texts belonging to different speech styles can be aimed:

To inspire or to motivate

To teach

To impart information

To explore or to debate ideas

To entertain

The majority of them, however, may include a combination of several purposes.

As far the spontaneous speech is concerned, it is in most cases a face-to-face interaction between two or several people. It also provides a variety of aims and situations, and the most common forms (or types) are these:

Question-answer interaction (interview)

Conversing (small talk, discussion)

Debating (dispute)

Each of them has "communication cooperation" as its underlying principle, its vehicle and a guarantee for successful communication.

Popular science text is one of the variations of prepared speech, it belongs to the neutral style of pronunciation. It combines some features that are characteristic of its co-variations: it gives factual information like the news-reading, but demands a higher degree of expressiveness to involve the listeners; it uses various manipulation techniques like the publicistic style text, but they are meant to improve the perception of information, and not to impose a certain point of view.

Professor T.V. Medvedeva classifies a popular science text as belonging to a publicistic phonetic style. She compares it with news text. It would be useful to compare it with lecturing style as well. The main aims of popular science text are:

to impart information

to entertain.

To reach them, the popular science text must satisfy the following conditions: it should be informative, science intensive, trustworthy and listener-oriented. Thus, the basic rules for the presenter of such text are as follows:

The presenter must catch the audience's attention and interest and keep it till the end of the presentation.

As the popular science text is aimed at educated people (but not professional audience), the information should be audible, all the terms should be explained and thesis illustrated.

To reach the goals mentioned above, the presenters use the methods based on the psychological researches. For example, the peculiarities of human aural perception depend on the pitch alterations and the duration of the sound signal. Rhythm and pausation also influence the perception. The reasons for this lie in the mental peculiarities of the human subconscious and, therefore, such peculiarities are the feature inherent in any listener. The experimental data proves that a long, loud sounds and following a pause can draw the listeners' attention. The low pitch of the voice makes the perception of information easier. The raised pitch helps to draw the listener's attention.

Background noises are also important. E.S. Kudinova in her article "Verbal and nonverbal interaction in communication" remarks that "Sounds and their intensity also have significant effect upon the process of communication... Music can calm down or excite".

Referring to the examples of popular science discourse we could recollect the films produced by BBC or the Discovery channel and other companies which are known for their everlasting popularity among the viewers of all ages. In the majority of cases the text is read by male speakers (which improves the perception), it is accompanied by an appropriate soundtrack.

As live performances are concerned, when the lecturer is speaking directly facing the audience (and to some extent in the cases when the anchorperson or the interviewed person appears in the frame), there appears another factor affecting the perception of the information – facial expressions and gestures of the speaker. Non-verbal actions convey a significant amount of information; meanwhile, non-verbal and prosodic features of the speech are mutually determined. E.S. Kudinova writes: 'In the communication process the kinetic means perform specific informational function. <...> The following functions of gestures have pragmatic meaning: establishing a contact, establishing the feedback, self-presentation, social orientation, motivating function, regulating function. <...> Expressive functions are: emphatic, emotive and adaptive functions' A remarkable thing is that the quality of aural recognition of different types of linguistic manipulation (order, request, begging, threat etc.) is worse than when videorecordings are used.

Gestures have emphatic, emotive and regulative functions. The nature of interaction of kinetic and prosodic means is determined by the aim of the utterance. One of the interesting points of this interaction is the opportunity to discern lies if prosodic and kinetic signs do not match: even a trained person is unable to control micromotion of facial muscles and some minor gestures, what is immediately noticed by our subconscious.

The next goal is to make information easily understandable. It is realised mostly through lexical and grammatical means. Yet intonation has specific functions that make the text easy to be perceived by the non-professional audience. O.F. Kryvnova says that 'Under the terms of semantic and syntactic complexity, diversity and linearity of the scientific text, syntactic and organizing functions of intonation obtain a particular functional importance for the perception and understanding of the text. T.M. Nikolaeva has noted an increasing amount of the instances of accentual highlighting in the reproduced scientific discourse and points out the fact that general system of accentual highlighting in oral scientific discourse is a coherent system where the limits are drawn the highlighting of the initial syntactic words and establishing the informational reference points and giving qualification statements.

One of the most important problems is division into paragraphs. Professor T.I. Shevchenko writes: 'The leading role in the division into paragraphs is played by the contrastive pitch alteration and the long pause'. According to her point of view, the paragraphs' boundaries are explicitly marked by prosodic means, those primarily which attract the listener's attention more effectively.

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